

In 1979, host plants of rice water weevil were reported; 16 were grasses, including *Paspalum distichum*, *B. mutica*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *E. colona*, *Leptochloa fascicularis*, and *Leptochloa* sp.

Other principal hosts were *Cyperus iria* and *C. esculentus*. Because the irrigation system in Sur del Jibaro uses dams, *Eichhornia paniculata* and *E. crassipes* also are important host plants.

Among the new *L. brevirostris* host plants that we identified, graminaceous species were more abundant (see table). Both adults and larvae fed on those weeds. □

Accelerative effect of juvenoids and precocene-II on diapause breaking of the larvae of three stem borers (SB)

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Larvae of *Scirpophaga incertulas*, *Chilo auricilius*, and *C. partellus* were collected

by incising the tillers of rice stubble in Dec to Feb 1982-83. Juvenoids hydroprene, methoprene, and precocene-II were applied topically in acetone dilutions at 1µl of the solution/larva. One µl pure acetone was applied in the control treatment. Larvae were reared in individual 5- × 0.5-cm glass tubes plugged with moist cotton and wrapped with black paper. The tubes were put inside a rearing chamber kept at 23 ± 1°C, 70-

80% relative humidity, and an 11-13 h lightdark cycle,

In the control treatment, *S. incertulas*, *C. auricilius*, and *C. partellus* moths developed in Feb-Mar, Feb, and Jun. In treated populations, moths developed earlier (see table), suggesting that these chemicals may accelerate diapause breaking of these stem borer larvae. The intensity of their effect may differ by species. □

Moth appearance from overwintering larvae treated topically with juvenoids and precocene-II, West Bengal, India.

Species	Dose ^a (µg/ individual)	Individuals (no.)		Moth appearance (%), 1982-83								
		Treated	Molted	Dec		Jan		Feb		Mar	Apr-May	Jun
				1-15	16-31	1-15	16-31	1-15	16-29	1-15	16-30	1-15
<i>S. incertulas</i>	H 10	8	3	67	33							
	H 100	36	12	8	8	83						
	M 10	10	2	100								
	M 100	37	9	67	33							
	C	25	12					17	75	8		
<i>C. auricilius</i>	H 100	40	32		53	47						
	H 200	48	40		100							
	P 50	26	20		50	50						
	P 100	46	23		44	57						
	P 150	46	24		63	38						
	C	25	21				100					
<i>C. partellus</i>	H 100	30	20					60	25	15		
	H 200	35	20		14	86						
	P 50	10	7				71	29				
	C	10	10									100

^aH = hydroprene, M = methoprene, C = control, P = precocene-II.

Life cycle of *Marasmia patnalis*, a leaf folder (LF) of rice in the Philippines

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From Oct to Mar 1984, caterpillars of *Marasmia patnalis* Bradley (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) were observed folding and damaging rice leaves at IRRI. This LF species is widely distributed in Southeast Asia. However, it has escaped attention of rice entomologists because of superficial similarity to the more commonly known LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*.

We studied the life cycle and habits of *M. patnalis* in the greenhouse at 26-34°C

with 70-80% relative humidity. Gravid female moths collected from the field

Life cycle of LF *Marasmia Patnalis* reared on TN1 rice, IRRI, 1984.

Character	Duration ^a (d)		Survival (%)
	Range	Average	
Egg	4-5	4	92.3
Larva	21-25	23	88.0
Prepupa	1-2	1	- ^b
Pupa	7-11	9	74.0
Total development period	33-43	37	
Adult longevity			
Male	4-3	3	
Female	5-7	5	

^an = 60 males and 60 females. ^bNo data.

were used for biological studies. More eggs were laid on the upper than the lower leaf surfaces. Eggs were laid singly or in groups of 2 to 9, groups of 2 being most common. Sometimes eggs were found on leaf sheaths. Incubation period was 4 d (see table). The larvae passed through 6 instars in 23 d. The first-instar

larvae, feeding in groups, scrape the leaf surface. They prefer young rice seedlings. The second-instar larvae fold leaves and feed within the fold. Feeding by all instars is on parenchyma tissue (between veins). Larvae did not feed on bundle sheath and sclerenchyma tissue.

Pupation is within a silken cocoon,

most commonly between two leaves that have been tied together. Pupation occurs in 9 d at the base of inner tillers.

Adult emergence was most frequent at 2200-2400 h. Male to female ratio was 2:1 (n = 80). Females laid about 120 eggs. Development period and percent survival at different stages are in the table. □

Oviposition of rice whorl maggot as influenced by azolla

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Interest in azolla, which covers the water surface in flooded rice fields, as an N source is increasing. Oviposition by RWM *Hydrellia philippina* is higher on

plants growing above open water. Close planting decreases oviposition and subsequent RWM damage.

In 1983 dry season, we studied the effect of azolla growth on RWM oviposition on rice plants. Plots (6 × 8 m) with azolla and without azolla were arranged in a randomized complete block design. Water depth was increased to 5 cm and azolla was incorporated. In 3 d, the water

surface was covered with azolla growth.

Before transplanting, water was drained slowly from the azolla plots to prevent azolla loss. Different transplanters were assigned to azolla-inoculated and uninoculated plots. Three days after transplanting (DT) water depth was increased to 5 cm and maintained there throughout the study period. Azolla was added to maintain a complete surface cover.

Plants in plots without azolla had four times more RWM eggs than those in inoculated plots (see table). As a result of the higher egg population, larval damage was significantly higher on plots without azolla. Percent damaged leaves on the azolla-inoculated plots was about 50% of that of the azolla-free plots. It is evident that azolla can be used in an integrated pest management program as a cultural method for controlling RWM. □

Effect of azolla on RWM oviposition, IRRI, 1983 dry season. ^a

	Eggs (no./hill)					Damaged leaves/hill (%) 25 DT
	5 DT	10 DT	15 DT	20 DT	25 DT	
With azolla	2.9	3.6	3.7	5.4	8.0	38
Without azolla	9.2	16.1	17.3	17.7	16.8	71
Difference ^b	6.3**	12.6**	13.6**	12.3**	8.8**	33**

^aAv of 8 replications. Sample size = 10 randomly selected hills/plot. ^b** = Significantly different at the 1% level by LSD.

Biology of the rice green leafhopper (GLH)

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The biology of the rice green leafhopper *Nephotettix malayanus* Ishihara and Kawase, found mainly on graminaceous weed *Leersia hexandra* Sw was studied in a 25±°C room using a susceptible japonica variety. GLH were originally collected in the subtropical Ryukyu Islands in southwestern Japan.

The mean incubation period of GLH eggs was 8.24 d. Female nymphs developed in 23.2 d, and the male in 21.9 d. Preovipositional period was 4.9 and females laid an average 117 eggs. Males lived 14.4 d and females 19.5 d.

A GLH generation is about 34 d and net reproductive rate is 101.97. The calculated capacity for population increase

Survival (l_x) and fertility (m_x) curves of GLH, Kyoto, Japan.

was 0.136.

The figure shows that GLH can live 46 d in the absence of natural enemies.

The fertility curve (m_x) gives the mean number of eggs laid/d and shows that oviposition peaked 33 d after hatching. □